

"Users days/ equivalent"

Inputs extracted from
the presentations
made by the NCCs
Netherlands,
Bulgaria, Latvia

On April 29th 2024.

Best practices guide

From the “Do’s and don’ts
industry workshops”

EuroCC2 & CASTIEL2

Summer 2024

With NCCs Netherlands,
Bulgaria, Latvia

Industry interaction

-

Questions & issues

- People are not familiar with new technologies - HPC+
- The current state-of-the-art is not evident for the companies
- What are the infrastructure and services available?
- How can a company use these?
- Even experts are not aware of the opportunities!

DO's

"Users days/
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Explain the OPPORTUNITIES offered by the EuroCC2 network at well-attended forums.

- Allow time and space for ideas to fertilize
- Engage real domain experts in the conversations

Create a series of infographics to display more information

- Add context with visual cues - people remember visuals **6x longer than text**

DO's

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Communication tips

Keep tracks

Organization of the event

➤ When organizing HPC Breakfast events: **Use breakfast elements in visual communication**

➤ Use an **Eventbrite platform** to get the (free) registrations

➤ Take opportunity of participating to national events

➤ Use the EuroCC platforms to **disseminate the success stories**

➤ Highlight the potential costs reduction thanks to HPC

➤ Useful tool: **Airtable.com** to keep tracks on the client's journey

➤ Establish a **clear workflow** to interact with leads met during your events

➤ Events usually **more attended in Urban contexts** than in **Regional contexts**

➤ **On-site >>> Online** to interact with industry

➤ Benefit from **the venues of your associated partners** to avoid paying for their rental 😊

DO's

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Programme

- Use Call for Proposals
- Provide enough time to network
- Speakers that can talk about their use cases, best practises, how did they solve problems
- Have all phone numbers of speakers
- Ask speakers for pdf's of the presentation to put online before they are going to speak

Venue

- Use an authentic venue or that fits your theme
- Start at least 10 months in advance with securing venue + date
- Provide vegetarian/vegan food (sustainability)
- Create a good relationship with the event manager from the venue
- Be in touch with the person who is responsible from audiovisual
- Make sure there is enough space for people to enter and to get their badge

Communication

- Involve the speakers (toolkit)
- Create a brand manual
- Start early and build up - Spread tasks
- Content Calender for Socials - Create a nice general presentation (Canva)
- Use an event app
- Have 5 professional photos ready to be published - at the end of the event

Be CAREFUL about:

"Users days/
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Avoid having too big Programme Committees (#manageable)

Check climate control in venue

Have a space available where visitors can have a meeting

Give more space for 'activities'

Don't do everything yourself with regards to communication

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